

Spinal Versus General Anesthesia for Transabdominal Preperitoneal (TAPP) Repair of Inguinal Hernia: Interim Analysis of A Controlled Randomized Trial

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Abstract:

This study conducted a controlled randomised experiment to assess the effectiveness and safety of spinal anaesthesia compared to general anaesthesia in 93 patients who had transabdominal preperitoneal (TAPP) repair for inguinal hernias at Patna Medical College & Hospital over a period of 14 months. The study revealed that spinal anaesthesia had notable benefits, such as improved haemodynamic stability, decreased postoperative discomfort, faster recovery times, and shorter hospital stays, in comparison to general anaesthesia. The positive effects of spinal anaesthesia were seen in the increased patient satisfaction levels. The results of this study provide evidence in favour of using spinal anaesthesia for TAPP hernia repair. This highlights the ability of spinal anaesthesia to improve patient outcomes and increase the efficiency of surgical procedures.

Keywords: Spinal Anesthesia, General Anesthesia, TAPP Inguinal Hernia Repair, Patient Outcomes.

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Introduction

Inguinal hernia repair is a frequently done surgical operation worldwide, utilising different surgical techniques and anaesthesia methods to enhance patient results and reduce complications [1]. The Transabdominal Preperitoneal (TAPP) approach is a minimally invasive procedure that effectively treats inguinal hernias, perhaps resulting in lower pain and faster recovery compared to conventional techniques [2]. Anaesthesia is crucial for the effectiveness of TAPP treatments as it affects both the patient's comfort during the operation and their recovery afterward [3].

The decision between spinal and general anaesthesia for TAPP repair of inguinal hernias is a crucial factor in clinical practice [4]. Spinal anaesthesia is recognised for its effectiveness in delivering sufficient pain relief while causing minimum impact on the body's overall functioning, which can result in faster recovery after surgery and shorter hospital stays [5]. Alternatively, general anaesthesia can be employed to guarantee full patient immobility and comfort, so minimizing the possibility of intraoperative awareness and creating a regulated setting for the surgeon [6,7].

This interim review of a controlled randomised experiment seeks to evaluate the results of spinal anaesthesia against general anaesthesia for TAPP inguinal hernia repair. The study examines various crucial characteristics, such as intraoperative stability, postoperative discomfort, recovery durations, and overall patient satisfaction. This research aims to offer evidence-based recommendations on the most effective anaesthesia strategy for TAPP hernia repair. The goal is to improve patient safety, comfort, and surgical effectiveness.

Methodology

Study Design: This controlled randomised experiment compared spinal and general anaesthesia in transabdominal preperitoneal (TAPP) inguinal hernia repair patients. The trial sought to establish the efficacy and safety of each anaesthesia type for this surgical method.

Participants: The study included 93 TAPP inguinal hernia repair patients. Adults 18 and older with inguinal hernia and qualified for TAPP repair were included. Patients with anaesthesia

contraindications, lower abdominal procedures, or coagulation issues were excluded.

Randomization and Blinding: Computer-generated randomisation sequences allocated patients to spinal or general anaesthesia groups. The allocation was 1:1. The intervention prevented anaesthesia providers from being blinded, while patients were blinded to the anaesthesia kind.

Intervention: Group: Standard bupivacaine was used for spinal anaesthesia. General Anaesthesia Group Standard protocols for general anaesthesia included propofol induction, isoflurane maintenance, and neuromuscular blocking.

Data Collection: Intraoperative factors such as operation length, haemodynamic stability, and complications were recorded. Postoperative recovery was determined by time to ambulation, Visual Analogue Scale discomfort, hospital stay, and complications.

Study Duration and Location: Patna Medical College & Hospital conducted the 14-month study. Data will be analysed with SPSS. Demographic and baseline variables will be summarised using descriptive statistics. The two groups will be compared using the Chi-square test for categorical variables and the Student's t-test for continuous variables. Statistically significant p-values are below 0.05.

Results

The study included 93 patients, 47 of whom received spinal anaesthesia and 46 generals. Both groups had similar age, gender, and baseline

clinical features. Participants averaged 52 years old and 80% were men.

Intraoperative Findings:

- **Surgery Duration:** The spinal anaesthesia group averaged 75 minutes and the general anaesthesia group 77 minutes.

- **Haemodynamic Stability:** Spinal anaesthesia patients had better stable haemodynamic parameters throughout surgery than general anaesthesia patients ($p = 0.02$).

Postoperative Recovery: Spinal anaesthesia patients recovered faster and ambulated 4 hours after surgery, compared to 6 hours for general anaesthesia patients ($p = 0.01$). Postoperative pain levels were considerably reduced in the spinal anaesthesia group at 2, 4, and 24 hours ($p < 0.05$).

Average Hospital Stay: The spinal anaesthesia group stayed 1.5 days compared to 2.5 days for the general anaesthesia group ($p = 0.003$).

Complications: No significant differences were found in intraoperative complications between the two groups.

Postoperative Complications: The spinal anaesthesia group had significantly decreased rates of nausea and urine retention compared to the general anaesthesia group ($p < 0.05$). A standardised discharge questionnaire showed higher patient satisfaction in the spinal anaesthesia group than in the general anaesthesia group ($p = 0.04$). This controlled randomised experiment found that spinal anaesthesia may improve haemodynamic stability, postoperative recovery, pain, and hospital stays for TAPP repair of inguinal hernia patients.

Parameter	Spinal Anesthesia Group	General Anesthesia Group	p-value
Number of Patients	47	46	-
Average Age (years)	52	52	-
% Male	80%	80%	-
Duration of Surgery (min)	75	77	0.65
Hemodynamic Stability	More stable	Less stable	0.02
Time to Ambulation (hours)	4	6	0.01
Pain Scores (2, 4, 24 hours)	Lower	Higher	<0.05
Duration of Hospital Stay (days)	1.5	2.5	0.003
Postoperative Complications (Nausea, Urinary Retention)	Less	More	<0.05
Patient Satisfaction Score	Higher	Lower	0.04

This table summarizes the comparative outcomes for the two groups across several intraoperative and postoperative measures, emphasizing statistically significant differences where applicable.

Discussion

This controlled randomised experiment offers valuable insights into the effectiveness and advantages of spinal anaesthesia compared to general anaesthesia for transabdominal preperitoneal (TAPP) repair of inguinal hernias [8]. The study yielded several crucial discoveries that

have profound significance for the use of surgical anaesthesia in clinical practice [9]. The group that received spinal anaesthesia showed more consistent haemodynamic measures throughout the surgery. This discovery is consistent with previous research indicating that spinal anaesthesia, which avoids the use of anaesthetic

drugs that affect the entire body and the need for airway interventions in general anaesthesia, may reduce changes in blood pressure during surgery [10,11]. This stability is especially advantageous in people who have cardiovascular diseases or are at risk of haemodynamic instability. The spinal anaesthesia group had substantially accelerated recovery durations and reduced pain scores, indicating the possibility for improved patient comfort and a faster resumption of normal activities. The benefits of spinal anaesthesia are due to its localised effect, which decreases the need for systemic opioids and the resulting side effects of general anaesthesia, such as nausea and drowsiness [12,13].

The decreased duration of hospitalisation reported in the group receiving spinal anaesthesia not only improves patient satisfaction but also presents a financially efficient strategy for healthcare providers [14]. Shortening the duration of hospitalisation can substantially save healthcare expenses and allocate more resources to other patients, which is vital in busy surgical facilities. The spinal anaesthesia group may experience higher patient satisfaction levels due to a combination of faster recovery, reduced pain, and shorter hospital stays. Measuring patient satisfaction is crucial since it is directly linked to better postoperative results and compliance with follow-up treatment [15,16].

The decreased occurrence of nausea and urine retention in the spinal anaesthesia group provides additional evidence for its favourable application as an anaesthesia approach in TAPP repairs [17]. These difficulties can cause a delay in the patient's release from the hospital, affect the patient's comfort, and lead to the need for further medical interventions, so making the recovery process after surgery more complicated. Although the study results are convincing, it is important to take into account some constraints. The lack of blinding for anaesthesia providers may introduce bias in the management of the patient during surgery and in the care provided after the operation. Furthermore, the study was carried out exclusively at one institution, thus restricting the applicability of the findings to other environments or populations with distinct demographic attributes [18].

Additional research is necessary to investigate the extended consequences linked to different types of anaesthesia in hernia repairs, such as recurrence rates and chronic discomfort. Conducting multi-center trials could yield more comprehensive data to support the conclusions observed in this investigation. This study highlights the potential benefits of using spinal anaesthesia instead of general anaesthesia for TAPP inguinal hernia surgery. Spinal anaesthesia should be regarded as a feasible and maybe preferable choice for

appropriate patients undergoing this type of surgery due to its ability to provide improved haemodynamic control, lower discomfort, and faster recovery times [19,20].

Conclusion

The controlled randomised trial comparing spinal and general anaesthesia for transabdominal preperitoneal (TAPP) inguinal hernia repair found that spinal anaesthesia improves haemodynamic stability, postoperative pain, recovery time, and hospital stay. These findings indicate that spinal anaesthesia improves immediate postoperative outcomes, patient satisfaction, and hospital resource utilisation. Spinal anaesthesia may revolutionise TAPP inguinal hernia repair due to these benefits.

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